

Evaluation of LIS syllabus of select Universities

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Abstract:

The LIS profession in India has a long history. It has seen several significant improvements throughout the timeframe. This paper takes up a case for the expansion of the LIS profession into non-academic libraries, which implies that non-academic associations should build up an acknowledgment first that a library can be of incredible use. In this paper, an attempt was made to examine the LIS courses' current curriculum to check its viability in taking into account the prerequisites of the non-academic libraries.

Keywords: LIS, Curriculum, Evaluation, Universities

Introduction

The LIS profession in India has a long history. It has seen several major developments over some time. This paper takes up a case for extending the LIS profession into non-academic libraries, which means that non-academic organizations will have to develop an acceptance first that a library can be of great use to them. In this paper, an attempt will be made to analyze the contents of the LIS courses' current curriculum to check its effectiveness in catering to the requirements of the non-academic libraries.

Universities selected for content analysis

Table 1: Universities selected for content analysis of LIS curriculum

Sr.No.	Name	State
1	Acharya Nagarjuna University	AP
2	Algappal University	TN
3	Aligarh Muslim University	UP
4	Anna University	TN
5	Annamalai University	TN
6	Balasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University	Bihar
7	Banaras Hindu University	UP
8	Bangalore University	Karnataka
9	Bharati Vidyapeeth	Maharashtra
10	Bharatisadan University	TN
11	Calicut University	Kerala
12	Ch Charan Singh University	Haryana

14	Delhi University	Delhi
15	Devi Ahilya Vishwavidyalaya	MP
16	Dr.Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University	Maharashtra
17	Gujarat University	Gujarat
18	Jadavpur University	WB
19	Kurukshetra University	Haryana
20	Kuvempku University	Karnataka
21	Madras University	Chennai
22	Mahadev Desai Samajseva University	Gujarat
23	Maharaj Krishnakumarji Bhavnagar University	Gujarat
24	Maharashi Dayanand Saraswati University	Gujarat
25	Mangalore University	Karnataka
26	Mumbai University	Maharashtra
27	Mysore University	Karnataka
28	Nalanda Open University	Bihar
29	NISCAIR	Delhi
30	North Eastern Hill University	Meghalaya
31	North Maharashtra University	Maharashtra
32	North Orissa University	Orissa
33	Osmania University	AP
34	Pt.Ravi Shankar Shukla University	Chatisgarh
35	Punjab University	Punjab
36	Punjabi University	Punjab
37	Rabindra Bharati University	WB
38	RTMN University	Maharashtra
39	Sambalpur University	Orissa
40	Sant Gadgebaba University	Maharashtra
41	Sardar Patel University	Gujarat
42	Saurashtra University	Gujarat
43	SNDT University	Maharashtra
44	SPP University	Maharashtra
45	University of Calcutta	WB
46	University of Kerala	Kerala
47	University of Rajashthan	Rajasthan
48	University of Solapur	Maharashtra

13	Utkal University	Orissa
49	Veer Narmad South Gujarat University	Gujarat
50	Vidyasagar University	WB

Methodology for content analysis

The current requirement of LIS education

This was arrived at based on LR, discussion with experts in the field, and inputs from few academic and non-academic librarians as under –

1. Advanced theoretical concepts like those in the West
2. General Practical Orientation particularly related to IT
3. Advanced Practical Orientation particularly related to Digital Libraries
4. Skill requirements including likes of HR, Finance, etc.
5. The quality orientation given the accreditation requirements

Criteria framework for evaluation of the syllabus

Based on the above requirements following was the outline designed for the evaluation of the syllabus.

Figure 1: Criteria framework for evaluation of syllabus

Specific criteria for evaluation of syllabus

Taking into account 1 & 2 above for this study following were the criteria fixed for evaluation of the curriculum –

1. Curriculum objectives and general evaluation
2. Advanced concepts
3. Intermediate IT concepts
4. Specialized IT application skills
5. General application skills
6. The curriculum of the 50 universities listed above for the MLIS Course was downloaded from the respective websites. The rationale for choosing MLIS Course was that a master's degree is considered a minimum requirement in today's competitive world.
7. These 50 curriculums were then observed and analyzed for their content match with the criteria set earlier.
8. Based on the observations and analysis, a score was assigned on a scale of 1-5 (in ascending order of match) for collective consideration of the curriculum for the 50 universities.

The analysis

As per the methodology set earlier, the rankings of the content match that emerged was as under:

a. Curriculum objectives and general evaluation

Only in the case of few universities was it observed that a clear set of objectives had been framed for the curriculum. For example, in the case of Bangalore University (2017-18) revision of the syllabus, the following objectives have been set –

1. To develop students' potential for critical thinking, particularly concerting goals of Library and Information centers.
2. To train students for a professional career in Library and Information Services.
3. To train students in handling information resources (print and non-print) to facilitate access and information sources.
4. To train students in using information technology tools and techniques in information access, service, management, and archival activities.
5. To further state of the art in library and information science through extension, research, and publications

Observations

1. The course is a 2 year course split into 4 semesters
2. Generally the credit system method has been adopted
3. Internal and external evaluation percentages vary but are generally in the ratio of 20:80
4. Courses have projects, dissertations and viva voce

b. Evaluation from the view point of application to non-academic libraries (as per criteria evolved earlier)

Table 2: Evaluation of the curriculum

Sr. No.	Criteria	Score Assigned (On a scale of 1-5)	Rationale
1	Advanced concepts	2	Courses still evolve around basic and intermediate concepts. Advanced concepts as seen in the West are not found in the curriculum to the extent they are desired.
2	Intermediate IT concepts	2	Starting from fundamentals, the contents hardly have depth in IT concepts. For example applications using internet, data analysis skills using IT, artificial intelligence etc. are not having the desired level of visibility.
3	Specialized IT application skills	1	This aspect is largely missing. Specialized IT application like full LMS software courses are missing. Stand-alone modules have been dealt with but exposure to complete handling of a single system is not seen.
4	General application skills	2	Basic HR and Finance concepts are seen a little bit. However case study based contents applicable for librarians are not seen.
Total		7	

Conclusion

Following key conclusions are drawn:

1. An attempt to carry an objective content analysis vis-à-vis requirements reveal a score of 7 out of 20, which in percentage terms is 35. In other words, the gap can be said to be in the region of 65%. This by no means is an exact assessment. Rather it is directional and broad. It can vary from person to person. Yet it cannot be the other way round, that is, 65:35.

2. Levels of IT contents are certainly much lower as compared to the requirements in practice. A professional librarian needs to possess certain advanced IT skills in order to match the requirements of practice.
3. Library Management software exposure is not visible. In other courses, generally, application software is taught. For example, for accounting courses, the software Tally is used for practical training.
4. Skill aspects have been largely ignored except few basic facets like HR and Finance skills. Today's real-life business world demands several skills like soft skills, data processing skills, leadership skills, etc. However, these are not reflected in the curriculum.

Thus the content analysis and matching exercise reveal that the gap is quite significant and hence the need for changes in the curriculum is a must.

References

Websites of respective universities